

Backpropagation from first principles for deep neural networks

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Abstract

The backpropagation algorithm of Rumelhart, Hinton & Williams is deduced from first principles for feed-forward deep neural networks. Appropriate notation is developed and presented to adequately describe the generic form of a deep, feed-forward neural network with an arbitrary number of hyper-parameters. A simple form of a loss function is used to illustrate how the algorithm is developed. The symbolic manipulation necessary to arrive at a form of the gradient of the loss function is presented as the guiding principle that naturally leads to the algorithm. The abstraction presented can be used to more easily derive the backpropagation algorithm for present and future neural network architectures of arbitrary complexity. Expanded forms of the generating equations are provided and an example is presented in detail.

1 Introduction

As this article is written, very capable deployments of artificial intelligence (AI) agents that are in the form of large language models (LLMs) are ubiquitous and are very rapidly permeating all aspects of modern society, from research to daily tasks, and from teaching to surveillance and healthcare. The fundamental work that contributed to this modern day (4th) industrial revolution has its roots on simple “feed forward” neural network architectures. Part of the early work was a seminal paper that presented the “backpropagation” algorithm. This algorithm, and importantly its modern implementations for a large variety of neural network architectures, is one of the most enabling innovations in the machine learning (ML) space, which is itself a fundamental building block of the artificial intelligence deployments.

In spite of its importance, the original article on backpropagation is largely unreadable by non-insider academics, with notions and language that is highly incompatible with the short attention span that present day teaching and learning practices promote. It is not a bold statement to say that many more people who are considered experts in the fields of ML and AI stand in front of audiences and show equations they themselves have never attempted to either program or understand fundamentally. This is obvious given that there are several errors that have propagated from an unknown, but primal, source to books and presentations that are accessible via the internet and are ranked highly by modern search-engine algorithms.

This writing is an effort to bring clarity to people who have been confused by the written presentation of the relevant material, which was not made any easier by the ubiquitous mistakes. In this writing, we start from describing the “architecture” of a deep, feed-forward neural network. We use notation that is appropriate for maintaining generality, sometimes at the expense of clarity. Because of that, we are intentionally verbose and pedantic at times. We borrow material and ideas from various sources, but give no attribution. We systematically proceed from describing how the network operates, to how it is supposed to be “trained” to become a function approximator. In

order to proceed to the backpropagation algorithm, we describe what a “loss function” is, and what role it plays in the training. From the logical deduction that follows the path of building the cost function and seeking to evaluate its parameters by fitting to data, the intuition of the backpropagation algorithm is also developed. And importantly, all steps are shown, with the final result being developing generic equations that can be implemented directly. With this process, we establish a mathematical pathway to building generic equations for implementing the backpropagation algorithm for arbitrary neural network architectures.

This written work is organized as follows. A large section describes the neural network architecture, the notation, and the deduction that leads to the backpropagation algorithm. A final section includes some concluding remarks. And some additional sections, in lieu of an appendix, are included that contain: (1) generic forms of the “derivatives” with respect to the input and the parameters of feed-forward neural networks, (2) expanded forms of some of the equations and expressions encountered in the main text, which are offered as clarifications, and (3) a worked out, tractable example.

2 The backpropagation algorithm

The basic idea should be easily understood by examining what is a deep neural network that is constructed by stacking layers of what is called a *feed forward layer*, which looks like this:

In this diagram, the input nodes to the network (dark dots on the left) are where numeric values are provided. Information flows through the network to the output nodes (black dots on the right). The number of inputs does not have to be equal to the number of outputs – these are *hyper parameters* established ahead of time based on the application. Between the sets of input and output nodes are layers of nodes, the so-called *hidden layers*. The number of nodes in each of the hidden layers does not have to be uniform through the network, but in this example the number is the same for all layers shown. I denote the inputs as the scalars $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$ and the outputs as the scalars $\{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_M\}$. The number of hidden layers is L , and the number of nodes in each of those layers is n ; these are also hyper parameters dictated ahead of time.

Each node of a given hidden layer collects the output of all nodes from the previous layer as a weighted sum, adds a bias term, and passes the sum as an argument to an *activation function* to produce the output of this specific node at this layer. It is customary to denote the sum of the weighted inputs and bias as z_j , where j is the index of the node in the layer. (The z_j terms are sometimes called *pre-activations*.) The activation function is usually denoted by $\sigma(\cdot)$, and its output is: $a_j = \sigma(z_j)$. The scalar a_j is the value that is the output of node j of the present layer, which is to be passed to the nodes in the next layer. (Not surprisingly, the a_j values are sometimes

called *activations*.)

The notation begins to get messy once we start keeping track of the specific layers with superscripts placed in parentheses. I denote the present layer by the index l , and we expect that any quantity indexed by $l-1$ is at the previous layer to layer l . (This can be ambiguous, as the notation can be different in different documents.) For an arbitrary layer l , the equation for the input to a node j looks like this:

$$z_j^{(l)} = \sum_{k=1}^{n^{(l-1)}} w_{jk}^{(l)} a_k^{(l-1)} + b_j^{(l)} \quad (1)$$

This equation represents with $z_j^{(l)}$ the components of the *vector* of pre-activations, $z^{(l)}$, which are arguments to the activation functions at each of the nodes j of layer l . The “inputs” to this layer are the activations from the previous layer, which are superscripted with $l-1$ to indicate the layer they came from.¹ The summation extends to $n^{(l-1)}$ nodes, and the notation here implies that layers do not necessarily have the same number of nodes. To avoid confusion we note that when passing these $z_j^{(l)}$ scalar values to the activation function, $\sigma(\cdot)$, this is done component by component of the vector $z^{(l)}$. And we further note that the doubly subscripted $w^{(l)}$ indicates that this is the (generally non-square) *matrix* of weights that are associated with node-to-node connections between adjacent layers; this is how it is commonly visualized, and it sometimes appears as a confusing *transpose*. The *biases* parameters for each of the neurons are represented by the components of the vector $b^{(l)}$. Generally, the activation function (whose output is an input to the next layer) is the same for all nodes of a given layer such that:

$$a_j^{(l)} = \sigma(z_j^{(l)}) \quad (2)$$

The architecture of this neural network makes the final output vector y be a *function composition* through the nesting effect of the stacked layers of neurons. If we think of x as the input vector, and each of the layers as functions of compatible preimage and output spaces and denoted by $f_l(\cdot)$, we can express this as:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= f_o(f_L(f_{L-1}(\dots f_2(f_1(x)) \dots))) \\ &= f_o \circ f_L \circ f_{L-1} \circ \dots \circ f_2 \circ f_1(x) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The subscripts to the functions $f_l(\cdot)$ are arranged such that each of these vector-valued functions represents a mapping from the “inputs” into a given layer to the “outputs” of that layer – they absorb the summations and the component-by-component activation function given by Eqs. (1) and (2) respectively. The outer function has the subscript o , and it is special because it does not involve an activation function, and has the form given by Eq. (1). (The output layer can involve an activation function, but not in this network.)

This is a good point to express the neural network more explicitly, so that ambiguities are removed, and such that it is easier to understand how the neural network can be *trained*. The $f_l(\cdot)$ functions that are nested are a combination of matrix multiplication and non-linear functions. One nuanced thing about the matrix multiplication part is that in the literature we encounter notation like: $W^{(l)} a^{(l-1)}$, where $W^{(l)}$ is a non-square matrix of weights at layer l that operates on the vector of outputs of the previous layer, $a^{(l-1)}$, and there is no mention of the bias terms (which should be a vector). This notation embeds the vector of biases as the last column of the matrix $W^{(l)}$, and the implication here is that when the matrix-vector operation takes place, an additional component is added at the bottom of the $a^{(l-1)}$ (and also the x) vectors, which is set to 1. Then, the biases become part of the matrix of weights to ease the notation imposed by Eq. (1), but this is purely

¹This is not conventional notation in the literature, but it is in Wikipedia and I prefer it this way.

by convention.² This allows us to express the neural network compactly as:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= f_o \circ f_L \circ f_{L-1} \circ \dots \circ f_2 \circ f_1(x) \\ &= W^o \tilde{\sigma}_L(W^{(L)} \tilde{\sigma}_{L-1}(\dots W^{(3)} \tilde{\sigma}_2(W^{(2)} \tilde{\sigma}_1(W^{(1)} \tilde{x}))) \dots) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Here I used \tilde{x} to indicate that x was endowed with an additional row that is 1. And I also used $\tilde{\sigma}$, making it a function that after operating component-by-component to the components of the input, it endows its output with a row of 1, such that the subsequent matrix-multiplication that embeds the biases makes sense.³

Let's take this a step further and define functions $M_l(\cdot)$ that represent matrix multiplication, taking a vector as an argument, and where the argument to such a function is operated on by the non-square matrix $W^{(l)}$. I will also have this function internally endow the input vector with the additional row that is 1, to keep this aspect opaque in terms of the notation. The indices are there to imply that each function is different at each layer l of the network –having compatible preimage and output spaces for inputs and preactivations between layers– and it has its own parameters. Now we can re-write Eq. (4) in terms of compositions of simpler functions:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= f_o \circ f_L \circ f_{L-1} \circ \dots \circ f_2 \circ f_1(x) \\ &= \underbrace{M_o}_{f_o} \circ \underbrace{\tilde{\sigma}_L \circ M_L}_{f_L} \circ \underbrace{\tilde{\sigma}_{L-1} \circ M_{L-1}}_{f_{L-1}} \circ \dots \circ \underbrace{\tilde{\sigma}_2 \circ M_2}_{f_2} \circ \underbrace{\tilde{\sigma}_1 \circ M_1}_{f_1}(x) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

And I also no longer use the “tilde” functions, $\tilde{\sigma}(\cdot)$, as the $M_l(\cdot)$ functions take care of the additional row internally, and the new “bar” $\bar{\sigma}(\cdot)$ functions are vector-valued but still operate component-by-component on their input vector to produce the vector of activations. For clarity, let's be more explicit with the functions in Eq. (5) by listing their domain and codomain:

$$\begin{array}{ll} M_1 : \mathbb{R}^N \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n^{(1)}} & \bar{\sigma}_1 : \mathbb{R}^{n^{(1)}} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n^{(1)}} \\ M_2 : \mathbb{R}^{n^{(1)}} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n^{(2)}} & \bar{\sigma}_2 : \mathbb{R}^{n^{(2)}} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n^{(2)}} \\ & \vdots \\ M_L : \mathbb{R}^{n^{(L-1)}} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n^{(L)}} & \bar{\sigma}_L : \mathbb{R}^{n^{(L)}} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n^{(L)}} \\ M_o : \mathbb{R}^{n^{(L)}} \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n^M} & \end{array}$$

Take a moment to absorb how the sizes N , $n^{(\cdot)}$, M are used to specify the spaces.

One interesting thing about the form of Eq.(5) is that the $M_l(\cdot)$ functions are *affine*, which means they are “linear-like”. And the interesting consequence of this is that any derivatives taken with respect to their parameters (the $W^{(l)}$ matrices that are implied by our notation) end up being either the function's argument, or are equal to 1. (They are the $a_j^{(l-1)}$ when we differentiate with respect to any of the elements of the first few columns of $W^{(l)}$, which are the $w_{jk}^{(l)}$ weights, and 1 when differentiating with respect to the elements of the last column, which are the biases embedded in the matrix and always multiply the number 1.) Based on our earlier notation, the arguments to $M_l(\cdot)$ are the vectors of activations, $a_i^{(l-1)}$ that are inputs to layer l .

Training a feed-forward neural network

In order to be able to train a feed-forward neural network like this, the weights and biases that parameterize each layer have to be considered as unknowns, and we somehow have to compute values for them. Because a neural network is a *function approximator*, we can think of estimating

²This is like the use of translations or *homogeneous coordinates* in computer graphics.

³The mental acrobatics are good for keeping up with notation, which will be proven useful.

the unknown parameters of the network by *fitting* to some data. The notion of a *loss function*, also known as a *cost function*, C , is useful. Suppose that we have several data points, which are given as a set of input-output vector pairs: $\{(x^{(1)}, q^{(1)}), (x^{(2)}, q^{(2)}), \dots\}$, where the superscripts are there to act as an index in the dataset. We can construct a simple convex loss function as:

$$C = \sum_m |r^{(m)}|^2 = \sum_m |y(x^{(m)}) - q^{(m)}|^2 = \sum_m \sum_{i=1}^M (y_i(x^{(m)}) - q_i^{(m)})^2 \quad (6)$$

The total loss is the sum of the squared length of the residual vector for each data point, and if the neural network perfectly reproduced the outputs it would be zero. The notation here has the neural network, $y(\cdot)$, ingest each of the $x^{(m)}$ vectors to form the residual, which is a vector whose length should be zero. The loss function, C , is a function of all the weights and biases that parameterize the network. It is “convex” in the sense that any departure from the data increases the loss function, however, this function is not convex in the network’s parameters (hidden inside y).

Ultimately we are going to have to solve a non-linear minimization problem of the form:

$$\theta = \underset{\theta \in \mathbb{R}^K}{\operatorname{argmin}} [C(\theta)]$$

where we have stacked in the vector θ all K parameters $w_{jk}^{(l)}, \beta_j^{(l)}$ of the neural network in contiguous blocks labeled $\theta^{(l)}$. A simple approach is to use the *gradient descent* algorithm, which starts from an initial guess for θ and iterates to some convergence criterion using a *learning rate*, α , via the update equation:

$$\theta^{\text{new}} \leftarrow \theta^{\text{old}} - \alpha \nabla_{\theta} C$$

where $\nabla_{\theta} C$ is the gradient of the loss function with respect to the network parameters. This algorithm may not be the best to use, however, all variants involve the gradients of the loss function. And gradients of the loss function involve the Jacobian of the function that is $y(x)$ with respect to the network’s parameters, which is what we need to focus on.

Derivatives (Jacobian) of the neural network function

The function composition given by Eq. (5) is parameterized by the network’s parameters that are embedded in the $M_l(\cdot)$ functions as $W^{(l)}$. I will temporarily use the vectors $\theta^{(l)}$ to indicate that we took the elements of each matrix $W^{(l)}$ and stacked them in a column. (This will help with not having to deal with derivatives with respect to matrix elements for the time being.) These vectors make up the K -sized θ vector that parameterizes the entire network, and we associate each one with a single $M_l(\cdot)$ function. Then, we use square brackets $[]$ to indicate that each vector-valued function $M_l(\cdot)$ is parameterized by $\theta^{(l)}$, and re-write the equation for the network in the conveniently verbose function composition form:

$$y(x) = M_o[\theta^{(o)}] \circ \bar{\sigma}_L \circ M_L[\theta^{(L)}] \circ \bar{\sigma}_{L-1} \circ M_{L-1}[\theta^{(L-1)}] \circ \dots \circ \bar{\sigma}_2 \circ M_2[\theta^{(2)}] \circ \bar{\sigma}_1 \circ M_1[\theta^{(1)}](x) \quad (7)$$

The notation here should be easy to understand if we look at the first operation, corresponding to the matrix-vector multiplication-like affine function $M_1(\cdot)$, which is parameterized by $\theta^{(1)}$ and ingests x . An alternative, and perhaps more proper notation, would be to write it like this: $M_1(\theta^{(1)}; x)$, but you see how the $[]$ notation is friendly to the function composition notation of Eq. (5), which is more useful.

Now suppose that we want to take a derivative of the output vector y with respect to a single parameter of the network, which is a component of the generic vector $\theta^{(l)}$ corresponding to the layer

l of the network. I will denote this variable by λ . Because $y(x)$ is a vector, we are expecting to compute a vector $\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} y$, which is the derivative with respect to the variable λ of each component of $y(x)$ stacked in a column. Assuming that all σ functions in the composition that forms the vector y are differentiable, we can write:

$$\underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} y(\theta, x)}_{\text{vector}} = \nabla_{\theta} y \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \theta = \underbrace{\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} y(\theta^{(o)}, \theta^{(L)}, \theta^{(L-1)}, \dots, \theta^{(l)}, \dots, \theta^{(2)}, \theta^{(1)}, x)}_{\text{relevant columns of the Jacobian } \nabla_{\theta} y} \cdot \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \theta^{(l)}}_{\text{vector}}$$

This equation shows the derivative of the vector function y with respect to a component of $\theta^{(l)}$, and the Jacobian matrix is dotted (matrix-vector product) with the vector whose components are the derivatives of the individual components of $\theta^{(l)}$ with respect to the arbitrary variable λ . This is the chain rule of differentiation from vector calculus⁴, and we are just being proper with differentiation with respect to an intermediate vector. The right-most vector of derivatives with respect to λ simply picks a single column of the matrix $\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} y$. By stepping through layers, l , and going down the list of parameters in a given layer through the dummy variable λ , we can extract all derivatives of the vector-valued output function y that we are after.

In computing the Jacobian with respect to the vector of parameters $\theta^{(l)}$ at layer l , it is convenient to use Eq. (7). By inspecting the function composition that needs to be differentiated we observe that in the nested sequence expressed as “ $\dots \circ \bar{\sigma}_{l+1} \circ M_{l+1} \circ \bar{\sigma}_l \circ M_l \circ \bar{\sigma}_{l-1} \circ M_{l-1} \circ \dots$ ” and centered here at the arbitrary function M_l , everything to the right of M_l is the M_l function’s argument, and we will denote this by the vector $a^{(l-1)}$. This vector is obviously a function of everything to the right of M_l , and is parameterized by several $\theta^{(l)}$ vectors. But differentiation with respect to $\theta^{(l)}$ will not affect the $a^{(l-1)}$ argument to the M_l function; it is a constant that can be evaluated starting from the input vector x , and going through the function compositions to the right of M_l . Now we can view Eq. (7) as:

$$y(x) = M_o[\theta^{(o)}] \circ \bar{\sigma}_L \circ M_L[\theta^{(L)}] \circ \bar{\sigma}_{L-1} \circ M_{L-1}[\theta^{(L-1)}] \circ \dots \circ \bar{\sigma}_l \circ M_l[\theta^{(l)}](a^{(l-1)}(x)) \quad (8)$$

In differentiating with respect to $\theta^{(l)}$, roughly speaking, we will need to take a derivative of the left most function, M_o , with respect to its argument, and multiply by the derivative of the argument with respect to $\theta^{(l)}$. Formally, this needs to be done by applying the vector form of the chain rule. Looking at the M_o function abstractly first, because it is vector-valued and its argument is a vector, we will need to compute the Jacobian matrix of derivatives, $\nabla_{\xi} M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi)$, where ξ is a dummy variable for the vector argument. (Recognize that this is because it is the argument to this function that is affected by $\theta^{(l)}$.) Then, we need to compute the Jacobian of the argument (which we can write as $a^{(L)}$ based on earlier notation) with respect to $\theta^{(l)}$, which is $\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} a^{(L)}$. Finally, matrix-matrix multiplication of these Jacobians gives as the gradient of $y(x)$ with respect to $\theta^{(l)}$ (a Jacobian), which is expressed by the notation heavy form:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} y(x) = \left(\nabla_{\xi} (M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi)) \right) \nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} a^{(L)} \quad (9)$$

There are a few things to note about this equation. The left-hand side is a (non-square) matrix because y is a vector and $\theta^{(l)}$ is the vector in which we stacked all parameters of layer l . The number of rows is M , which is the number of components of the vector y , and the number of columns is the number of network parameters at layer l , or $n^{(l)}(n^{(l-1)} + 1)$. The left Jacobian matrix on the right-hand side is evaluated at constant $\theta^{(o)}$ and fixed $\xi = a^{(L)}$, except that the M_o function is affine

⁴Had we used the matrix of weights, we would be dealing with derivatives with respect to matrices, which are actually used in affine functions here, and that would be messy.

(or linear-like) in ξ , and therefore the components of $a^{(L)}$ end up not appearing in this Jacobian matrix. That is, $\nabla_{\xi} M_o$ comprises only of elements of $\theta^{(o)}$ and 1s. The right-most Jacobian matrix is only a placeholder here, as it is a complicated expression that is the result of applying the vector form of the chain rule repeatedly until finally differentiating M_l with respect to $\theta^{(l)}$ as the final step.

At this point, it makes sense to start looking at this process in stages of differentiation of the argument followed by “multiplication” as part of repeatedly applying the chain rule. To calculate the Jacobian $\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} a^{(L)}$ we look at everything to the right of M_o in Eq. (8), and what we encounter first is $\bar{\sigma}_L$. Using ζ as a dummy variable for the vector input to $\bar{\sigma}_L(\cdot)$ we apply the chain rule to deduce a new form for the Jacobian that must be evaluated:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} a^{(L)} = \nabla_{\zeta}(\bar{\sigma}_L(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(L)}} \nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} z^{(L)}$$

The Jacobian matrix of derivatives of $\bar{\sigma}_L$ is diagonal because this function operates on its argument component by component (the i^{th} element of $\bar{\sigma}_L$ depends only on ζ_i , and therefore all other columns of the i^{th} row are zero). Therefore, the notation $\nabla_{\zeta} \bar{\sigma}_L$ denotes a diagonal matrix of the derivative of the componentwise activation function. And the value that each of those derivatives ingests is an element of the vector of preactivations of layer L , which we denoted by $z^{(L)}$ through Eq. (1).

Substituting this form of the Jacobian into Eq. (9) we get a new form of the gradient of $y(x)$ with respect to the vector of parameters at layer l , now given by:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} y(x) = \left(\nabla_{\xi} (M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi)) \right) \nabla_{\zeta}(\bar{\sigma}_L(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(L)}} \nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} z^{(L)} \quad (10)$$

Naturally, we need to continue reducing the abstraction that we are carrying in the right-most Jacobian matrix to an irreducible form, and this is done by repeated application of the chain rule. Again we look at Eq. (8) and observe that $z^{(L)} = M_L[\theta^{(L)}] \circ \bar{\sigma}_{L-1} \circ \dots$ is the form of the preactivation. Similarly to what was done in Eq. (9) with differentiating M_o , this intermediate right-most Jacobian matrix is:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} z^{(L)} = \left(\nabla_{\xi} (M_L[\theta^{(L)}](\xi)) \right) \nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} a^{(L-1)}$$

Substituting this in Eq. (10) gives the latest form of the gradient of $y(x)$ with respect to the layer l parameters as the Jacobian matrix:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} y(x) = \left(\nabla_{\xi} (M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi)) \right) \nabla_{\zeta}(\bar{\sigma}_L(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(L)}} \left(\nabla_{\xi} (M_L[\theta^{(L)}](\xi)) \right) \nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} a^{(L-1)} \quad (11)$$

Again the right-most Jacobian can be reduced, giving rise to a pattern of matrix-matrix multiplications that alternates between derivatives of the components of the M functions (which only depend on the $\theta^{(l)}$ vectors) and the $\bar{\sigma}$ functions (which only depend on activation vectors $a^{(l)}$) until layer l is reached.

For the arbitrary Jacobian we are after, we will eventually arrive to an expression of the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} y(x) = & \left(\nabla_{\xi} (M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi)) \right) \\
& \nabla_{\zeta} (\bar{\sigma}_L(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(L)}} \left(\nabla_{\xi} (M_L[\theta^{(L)}](\xi)) \right) \\
& \nabla_{\zeta} (\bar{\sigma}_{L-1}(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(L-1)}} \left(\nabla_{\xi} (M_{L-1}[\theta^{(L-1)}](\xi)) \right) \\
& \dots \\
& \nabla_{\zeta} (\bar{\sigma}_{l+1}(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(l+1)}} \left(\nabla_{\xi} (M_{l+1}[\theta^{(l+1)}](\xi)) \right) \\
& \nabla_{\zeta} (\bar{\sigma}_l(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(l)}} \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} (M_l[\theta^{(l)}](a^{(l-1)})) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where all terms are linked via matrix-matrix multiplication. The right-most Jacobian matrix is taken with respect to the network’s parameters at that layer. And because of the properties of the M_l function, this matrix will only depend on the evaluated activation vector from the previous layer, $a^{(l-1)}$, and will have some of its elements be 1. Using Eq. (12) combined with the fact that $\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \theta^{(l)}$ extracts only one column of the fully multiplied Jacobian matrix, we are able to obtain all gradients of $y(x)$ with respect to the network parameters. But at this point, this is tedious and arithmetically intense (and problematic) if implemented naïvely.

A second inspection of Eq. (12) is warranted to note that there are three types of derivatives taken, and they are with respect to ζ , ξ , and $\theta^{(l)}$. The interesting pattern that arises involves differentiation of a single vector-valued function with respect to $\theta^{(l)}$ for its corresponding layer (right-most matrix) as mentioned, and differentiation of all other functions with respect to ξ or ζ . All matrices are evaluated at fixed preactivations and activations as needed.

Gradients of the loss function

The choice of the loss function, C , given by Eq. (6) is very simple, and perhaps not the best. But constructing a loss function that works really well is a complicated topic. For this reason we will proceed with this loss function as a generic example. The gradient of the loss function with respect to the network parameters takes the form:

$$\nabla_{\theta} C = 2 \sum_m \sum_{i=1}^M (y_i(x^{(m)}) - q_i^{(m)}) \nabla_{\theta} y_i \Big|_{x^{(m)}} \tag{13}$$

The only non-trivial part of this expression is the gradient of the components of the neural network function, $\nabla_{\theta} y$, which needs to be evaluated with each $x^{(m)}$ input vector. This essentially completes the formulation of the problem, except that we would have to suffer through the sequence of operations of Eq. (12).

Before proceeding with any symbol manipulation, let’s visualize what this equation implies. And it helps to first annotate the figure depicting the feed-forward neural network architecture with labels for its parameters and showing hidden layer node counts. For example, in the following figure, the $\theta^{(2)}$ vector represents the $W^{(2)}$ matrix, and is made of $n^{(2)} \times (n^{(1)} + 1)$ parameters stacked in a column.

The left-hand side of Eq. (13) is a tall column vector of derivatives of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\theta} C &= \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1}, \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_K} \right)^T \\ &= \left(\underbrace{\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1^{(1)}}, \dots, \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1^{(2)}}}_{n^{(1)}(N+1) \text{ terms}}, \underbrace{\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1^{(2)}}, \dots, \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1^{(3)}}}_{n^{(2)}(n^{(1)}+1) \text{ terms}}, \dots, \underbrace{\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1^{(L)}}, \dots, \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1^{(o)}}}_{n^{(L)}(n^{(L-1)}+1) \text{ terms}}, \dots, \underbrace{\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1^{(L)}}, \dots, \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta_1^{(o)}}}_{M(n^{(L)}+1) \text{ terms}} \right)^T \end{aligned}$$

(I have used the transpose here to better fit the expression horizontally, where each derivative that appears is a scalar, with K rows making the tall vector.) And if we take the extra step to be verbose with what the derivatives of C with respect to each variable in the vector θ look like based

on Eq. (13). we can write:

$$\nabla_{\theta} C = \begin{pmatrix} 2 \sum_m \sum_{i=1}^M r_i^{(m)} \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial \theta_1^{(1)}} \Big|_{x^{(m)}} & (1^{\text{st}} \text{ layer}) \\ 2 \sum_m \sum_{i=1}^M r_i^{(m)} \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial \theta_2^{(1)}} \Big|_{x^{(m)}} & \\ \vdots & \\ 2 \sum_m \sum_{i=1}^M r_i^{(m)} \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial \theta_1^{(2)}} \Big|_{x^{(m)}} & (2^{\text{nd}} \text{ layer}) \\ 2 \sum_m \sum_{i=1}^M r_i^{(m)} \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial \theta_2^{(2)}} \Big|_{x^{(m)}} & \\ \vdots & \\ \vdots & \\ 2 \sum_m \sum_{i=1}^M r_i^{(m)} \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} \Big|_{x^{(m)}} & (l^{\text{th}} \text{ layer}) \\ 2 \sum_m \sum_{i=1}^M r_i^{(m)} \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} \Big|_{x^{(m)}} & \\ \vdots & \\ \vdots & \\ 2 \sum_m \sum_{i=1}^M r_i^{(m)} \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial \theta_1^{(o)}} \Big|_{x^{(m)}} & (\text{output layer}) \\ 2 \sum_m \sum_{i=1}^M r_i^{(m)} \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial \theta_2^{(o)}} \Big|_{x^{(m)}} & \\ \vdots & \end{pmatrix}$$

The first thing to recognize about this expression is that the gradient is a sum of gradients as computed for each of the $x^{(m)}$ instances (pull the summation over m outside of the vector). And therefore, we can work with one instance to make notation simpler, skipping the use of the (m) superscripts and the summation over m . (I will use this simpler notation with implied m summation only momentarily.)

The interesting thing to realize about the expression for each of the components of this gradient vector is that there is a sum of derivatives $\frac{\partial y_i}{\partial \theta_j^{(l)}}$ over the index i . This stems from the chain rule of differentiation of the loss function in Eq.(13), which, in vector form, stems from the dot product:

$$r^{(m)} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_j^{(l)}} y \right)_{x=x^{(m)}} = \left(r_1^{(m)}, \dots, r_M^{(m)} \right) \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_j^{(l)}} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial y_M}{\partial \theta_j^{(l)}} \end{pmatrix}_{x=x^{(m)}}$$

that naturally arises when differentiating $|r^{(m)}|^2$. We recognize the derivatives on the right-hand side as the vector $\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} y(\theta, x)$ where λ was a dummy parameter of the neural network; in this case λ is the j^{th} element of the $\theta^{(l)}$ vector of parameters. This vector of derivatives is also a single column of the Jacobian matrix of Eq. (12) as evaluated for the vector input $x^{(m)}$. Again, the terms involving derivatives that appear here are tedious to evaluate, with growing effort the smaller the layer index, l , gets, but Eq. (12) is the generic form that produces those terms.

This dot-product can be re-arranged, by the properties of inner products. If we swap the order of the vectors, making the residual a column vector and the vector of derivatives a row vector (ignoring the m index momentarily), we can write this scalar as:

$$r \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_j^{(l)}} y = \left(\frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_j^{(l)}}, \dots, \frac{\partial y_M}{\partial \theta_j^{(l)}} \right) \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \\ \vdots \\ r_M \end{pmatrix}$$

This is an expression that we can use for all rows of the gradient vector of the loss function, where each row corresponds to differentiation of the loss function with respect to the arbitrary parameter $\theta_j^{(l)}$. Making this ordering swap implies that we have specified that the gradient of the loss function of Eq. (13) in vector form is given in terms of a (conventional) matrix-vector product of the matrix $(\nabla_{\theta} y)^T$ and the r vector; we must make use of the transposed matrix to be consistent using this ordering of terms. And now we can write Eq. (13) like this:

$$\nabla_{\theta} C = 2 \sum_m \left(\nabla_{\theta} y|_{x^{(m)}} \right)^T r^{(m)} \quad (14)$$

The transpose of the gradient of the vector function y is needed because we replaced the summation over i that is implied by the row-wise dot products with the equivalent matrix-vector multiplication of conventional row/column ordering. Consequently, when the expression for the generic layer’s Jacobian matrix given by Eq. (12) is used to substitute for the $(\nabla_{\theta} y)^T$ matrix in Eq.(14), it is the transpose matrix of the long sequence of matrix-matrix multiplications that is needed. And an important consequence of that –which will be exploited later– is that the sequence of matrix-matrix multiplications that appears in Eq. (12) will have to be performed in reverse with the matrices transposed.⁵ This will naturally give rise to the *backpropagation* algorithm.

As a starting point, we consider the rows of the gradient vector of the loss function that correspond to the affine output layer indicated by the subscript o because they are the easiest to obtain. These last $M \times (n^{(L)} + 1)$ rows of the vector $\nabla_{\theta} C$ are given by the expression:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(o)}} C = 2 \sum_m \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(o)}} y|_{x=x^{(m)}} \right)^T r^{(m)} = 2 \sum_m \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(o)}} (M_o[\theta^{(o)}](a^{(L)}|_{x=x^{(m)}})) \right)^T r^{(m)}$$

Certainly this is a special layer because it does not involve activation functions, but this expression is still deduced from the generic form of Eq. (12). We simply consider the arbitrary layer, l , in Eq. (12) to be the output layer, o . The Jacobian is with respect to $\theta^{(o)}$ and evaluated with activations $a^{(L)}$, and that is all that is required.

There are several things to note about this extremely notation-heavy expression. The sum over m is taken over all pairs in the dataset; the $x^{(m)}$ have been forward propagated to instances of activations vectors, $a^{(L)}$, and the data, $y^{(m)}$, were used to form the residual vectors, $r^{(m)}$. The activation instances, $a^{(L)}$, are used to evaluate the instances of the gradient of the M_o function with respect to the network parameters, $\theta^{(o)}$, resulting in matrix instances whose elements are components of the $a^{(L)}$ vectors and 1s. Also note the transposition on the matrices in the matrix-vector operations inside the sum.

What this expression amounts to is the summation of “transformed residual vectors”, and these are the residuals, $r^{(m)}$, mapped by matrices whose elements are made of activations and 1s. In essence, the difference of the output, $y(x^{(m)})$, from the right answer, $q^{(m)}$, which is the error the network produces, is used to compute the gradient of the loss function with respect to this specific

⁵It is a property of matrix transposition to have $(A B C)^T = C^T B^T A^T$ for compatible matrices.

layer's parameters. All other parameters of the network that are not part of $\theta^{(o)}$ have contributed to the evaluation of the $\nabla_{\theta^{(o)}} M_o$ matrix because its elements are activations (and 1s) coming from layer L , and therefore involving all prior layers. Here, the notion that the error at the output was transformed by a function (a matrix, via a matrix-vector product) is also important to the backpropagation algorithm.

In a similar fashion, the rows of the loss-function gradient vector that correspond to the prior network layer, L , can be obtained. It should be obvious why layer L is a natural next layer to tackle; the number of matrix-matrix operations that are needed to compute those quantities based on Eq. (12) is the next smallest after those of the output layer. And the same process of performing matrix-vector operations is used here as well. The starting point is to express the Jacobian matrix $\nabla_{\theta^{(L)}} y(x)$, for layer L , based on Eq. (12). And because of how it will be used in Eq. (14), we need its transpose. Starting from Eq. (12) and considering $l = L$, the transpose of the Jacobian matrix becomes:

$$\left(\nabla_{\theta^{(L)}} y(x)\right)^T = \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(L)}} (M_L[\theta^{(L)}](a^{(L-1)}))\right)^T \nabla_{\zeta}(\bar{\sigma}_L(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(L)}} \left(\nabla_{\xi}(M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi))\right)^T$$

where the order of matrix-matrix operations was reversed, and transposes were used for the non-symmetric matrices that are the gradients of the M functions; the Jacobian of the componentwise activation function is diagonal, and is equal to its transpose. Two things should be noted about this expression. First, note that gradients of the two M functions are taken with respect to different variables. And second, the Jacobian matrix that is associated with the L layer's M_L function is evaluated using the activations that were the output of its prior layer, $L-1$. Inserting this expression in Eq. (14) allows us to extract the rows of the loss function gradient vector that correspond to the parameters of layer L . We have a matrix-vector operation, which can proceed right-to-left by first operating $\left(\nabla_{\xi}(M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi))\right)^T$ on $r^{(m)}$ to obtain an intermediate result, and proceeding with the remaining matrix-vector operations until the final vector –consisting of $n^{(L)} \times (n^{(L-1)} + 1)$ components– is obtained.

We can proceed with expressing the rows of the loss-function gradient vector that correspond to layer $L-1$, and in this way identify a pattern of error propagation through the network. Again, from Eq. (12) we first express the transpose of the Jacobian associated with layer $L-1$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(L-1)}} y(x)\right)^T &= \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(L-1)}} (M_{L-1}[\theta^{(L-1)}](a^{(L-2)}))\right)^T \nabla_{\zeta}(\bar{\sigma}_{L-1}(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(L-1)}} \\ &\quad \left(\nabla_{\xi}(M_L[\theta^{(L)}](\xi))\right)^T \nabla_{\zeta}(\bar{\sigma}_L(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(L)}} \\ &\quad \left(\nabla_{\xi}(M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi))\right)^T \end{aligned}$$

We use it in Eq. (14) to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\theta^{(L-1)}} C &= 2 \sum_m \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(L-1)}} y \Big|_{x=x^{(m)}}\right)^T r^{(m)} \\ &= 2 \sum_m \left[\left(\nabla_{\theta^{(L-1)}} (M_{L-1}[\theta^{(L-1)}](a^{(L-2)(m)}))\right)^T \right. \\ &\quad \nabla_{\zeta}(\bar{\sigma}_{L-1}(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(L-1)(m)}} \left(\nabla_{\xi}(M_L[\theta^{(L)}](\xi))\right)^T \\ &\quad \left. \nabla_{\zeta}(\bar{\sigma}_L(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(L)(m)}} \left(\nabla_{\xi}(M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi))\right)^T \right] r^{(m)} \end{aligned}$$

This equation sums the “mapped” residual vectors to form a block of components of the $\nabla_{\theta}C$ vector. The superscript (m) indicates that the residual vectors, $r^{(m)}$, have been mapped via matrix-vector multiplications by matrices that are formed by the corresponding instances of the preactivations and activations. But when observing this process as propagating from right to left, note that the early matrix-vector multiplications use the frozen $W^{(l)}$ data, while the final matrix-vector multiplication and the diagonal matrix multiplications (involving derivatives of the activation functions) use forward propagated data.

By observing what we did here, we can deduce a pattern that can be generalized for the block of the gradient’s components corresponding to the generic layer, l . In doing so, we will introduce some notation to de-clutter of some symbols – just as we got used to them. We start with the computation of the cost function gradient’s components corresponding to the output layer parameters. Recall that for one m instance, the matrix that maps $r^{(m)}$ to obtain the gradient of C with respect to $\theta^{(o)}$ is what we will define here as:

$$A_o^{(m)} := \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(o)}} (M_o[\theta^{(o)}](a^{(L)}|_{x=x^{(m)}})) \right)^T$$

This non-square matrix comprises of only components of the activation vector $a^{(L)}$ and 1s, and this is because the M_o function is differentiated with respect to the parameters $\theta^{(o)}$ and is evaluated at fixed $a^{(L)}$. The vector $a^{(L)}$ is evaluated by propagating $x^{(m)}$ through the network, and therefore it should be thought of as $a^{(L)(m)}$, where the (m) superscript indicates the data instance that was used to evaluate this vector of activations as it is produced by layer L . Now we have a simple-looking expression for the last set of rows of the cost function gradient vector that we previously derived, given by:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(o)}} C = 2 \sum_m \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(o)}} y|_{x=x^{(m)}} \right)^T r^{(m)} = 2 \sum_m A_o^{(m)} r^{(m)}$$

We proceed similarly for the rows of the cost function gradient corresponding to the parameters of layer L . First, we need to define notation for the matrix that takes part in the right-most matrix-vector multiplication, which is the transpose of the Jacobian matrix of the affine M_o function when differentiated with respect to its argument (represented by ξ). We have existing notation for this matrix, as we will see, but for now we just define a placeholder primed symbol for the transpose of the Jacobian matrix as:

$$M'_o := \left(\nabla_{\xi} (M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi)) \right)^T$$

Note that the elements of this matrix are only components of the vector $\theta^{(o)}$, which are parameters of the network’s output layer. Second, we define the diagonal matrix that is the Jacobian of the component-wise activation function, which is evaluated at fixed preactivations of the layer L , as:

$$D_L^{(m)} := \nabla_{\zeta} (\bar{\sigma}_L(\zeta)) \Big|_{\zeta=z^{(L)(m)}}$$

And finally, we make a familiar definition for the right-most matrix based on what was done for the output layer (all this stemming from Eq. (12) and transpositions) to express:

$$A_L^{(m)} := \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(L)}} (M_L[\theta^{(L)}](a^{(L-1)}|_{x=x^{(m)}})) \right)^T$$

With these definitions, we have a simple-looking expression for the rows of the cost function gradient vector that correspond to the L^{th} layer:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(L)}} C = 2 \sum_m \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(L)}} y|_{x=x^{(m)}} \right)^T r^{(m)} = 2 \sum_m A_L^{(m)} D_L^{(m)} M'_o r^{(m)}$$

Repeating the process for layer $L - 1$ and by making similar placeholder definitions, we can obtain an expression for the next set of rows of the cost function gradient vector:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(L-1)}} C = 2 \sum_m \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(L-1)}} y \Big|_{x=x^{(m)}} \right)^T r^{(m)} = 2 \sum_m A_{L-1}^{(m)} D_{L-1}^{(m)} M'_L D_L^{(m)} M'_o r^{(m)}$$

The pattern that arises starts by taking the expression for the rows of the gradient from the previous layer, $l - 1$, and simply: (1) replacing the left-most matrix $A_{()}$ with the corresponding $M'_{()}$ matrix, (2) including pre-multiplication by the diagonal matrix corresponding to activation functions, and (3) including the matrix-vector multiplication by an $A_{()}$ matrix from the left. For example, the next few rows of the gradient, corresponding to layer $L - 2$, are obtained by:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(L-2)}} C = 2 \sum_m \left(\nabla_{\theta^{(L-2)}} y \Big|_{x=x^{(m)}} \right)^T r^{(m)} = 2 \sum_m A_{L-2}^{(m)} D_{L-2}^{(m)} M'_{L-1} D_{L-1}^{(m)} M'_L D_L^{(m)} M'_o r^{(m)}$$

Finally, the expression for the rows of the gradient corresponding to a generic layer, l , is:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} C = 2 \sum_m A_l^{(m)} D_l^{(m)} M'_{l-1} D_{l-1}^{(m)} \dots M'_{L-1} D_{L-1}^{(m)} M'_L D_L^{(m)} M'_o r^{(m)} \quad (15)$$

along with the definitions for the matrices $A^{(m)}$, M' , and $D^{(m)}$.

The Backpropagation algorithm

At first, it is not obvious how Eq. (15) has granted us an advantage over the naive and tedious computation of the large Jacobian matrix of the neural network given by Eq. (12). However, we were building hints along the way that the operations that appear left-to-right in the equations will be performed right-to-left by a computer in practice. This by itself is not a large advantage until we recognize what aspect of this calculation can be re-used in an arithmetic computation with a practical computer.

There are two key observations that contribute to the power of the algorithm. The first is that preactivations and activations are used to form all $A^{(m)}$ and $D^{(m)}$ matrices that appear in Eq. (15). What this guides us to do is perform a “forward pass” of the $x^{(m)}$ data instance through the network to produce the vectors $y(x^{(m)})$ and $r^{(m)}$, while evaluating, and importantly *storing* to surplus memory, all the preactivations and activations. The second is that we can cascade the calculation of “mapped error vectors” from computing loss function gradient vector components corresponding to late layers to compute those corresponding to earlier layers in a “backwards pass”. For example, compare the expressions for the components of layers $l - 1$ and 1 as given by Eq. (15):

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\theta^{(l-1)}} C &= 2 \sum_m A_{l-1} D_{l-1}^{(m)} \dots M'_{L-1} D_{L-1}^{(m)} M'_L D_L^{(m)} M'_o r^{(m)} \\ \nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} C &= 2 \sum_m A_l^{(m)} D_l^{(m)} M'_{l-1} D_{l-1}^{(m)} \dots M'_{L-1} D_{L-1}^{(m)} M'_L D_L^{(m)} M'_o r^{(m)} \end{aligned}$$

Notice how the computation of the vector $D_{l-1}^{(m)} \dots M'_{L-1} D_{L-1}^{(m)} M'_L D_L^{(m)} M'_o r^{(m)}$ is common to both expressions. Therefore, to capitalize on this, the algorithm should be computing the vectors that are contributions to the loss function gradient components associated with (m) data instances starting from the output layer and proceeding backwards to the 1st layer in the backward pass.

Generally speaking but not necessarily in practice, an outer sweep over the (m) data instances should be established; this will be the “sum over m ” part of the expressions (\sum_m), and at each instance, part of the whole $\nabla_{\theta} C$ vector will be accumulated. For each m instance, the following

steps will be taken: (1) the data will be propagated through the network in a forward pass and preactivation and activation vectors will be built and stored, (2) the error vector, $r^{(m)}$, will be constructed, (3) the backward pass will begin. During the backward pass, first the mapped error vector $A_o^{(m)} r^{(m)}$ will be computed and its contribution to the components of the gradient of the loss function associated with the output layer will be accumulated. Then, an intermediate result $M'_o r^{(m)}$ prior to layer L will be computed and stored; let's denote this by the vector $\delta_o^{(m)}$. Subsequently, the contributions to the loss function gradient vector's components for layer L will be computed as $A_L^{(m)} D_L^{(m)} \delta_o^{(m)}$, and accumulated in the appropriate locations of the vector $\nabla_{\theta} C$. The next few steps are similar and repetitive: an intermediate result will be constructed and stored prior to layer $L - 1$, which will be $\delta_L^{(m)} = M'_L D_L^{(m)} \delta_o^{(m)}$, and the contribution to the layer $L - 1$ components, $A_{L-1}^{(m)} D_{L-1}^{(m)} \delta_L^{(m)}$, will be accumulated. There is a subtle point here as to whether intermediate results should be of the form $\delta_o^{(m)} = M'_o r^{(m)}$, $\delta_L^{(m)} = M'_L D_L^{(m)} \delta_o^{(m)}$ and generically $\delta_l^{(m)} = M'_l D_l^{(m)} \delta_{l+1}^{(m)}$ as presented here, or the more arithmetically efficient $\delta_L^{(m)} = D_L^{(m)} M'_o r^{(m)}$ and generically $\delta_l^{(m)} = D_l^{(m)} M'_{l+1} \delta_{l+1}^{(m)}$. We will always choose the most efficient implementation, but the main point here on backpropagation is illustrated better with the former definition given what the notation looks like.

3 Concluding remarks

Backpropagation is not the only algorithm that can be used to train deep neural networks, and without appropriate modifications and “regularization” can even be ineffective. Exploring optimization and robustness augmentations of the algorithm falls outside of the scope of this writing. However, it should be emphasized that practitioners should study such constructs in depth as well.

The literature is already vast as of this writing, and is growing rapidly. For an overview of the most important concepts (with examples), as well as a list of sources and references, Simon D. Prince’s “Understanding deep learning” is a good starting point.

In this material, the choice was made to perform the symbolic manipulation that involved differentiation by stacking parameters in a long vector. It should be obvious how this offered simplifications, as we did not have to show differentiation with respect to matrix elements. Recall the lack of discussion of coordinate systems and bases, which are essential in performing such computations. For this reason, supplementary material is included at the end of this writing which shows what those derivatives are. The reader can draw connections to what is in the literature – and identify the errors that have permeated it. In that small section there is also some discussion about how those derivatives are computed and how components are extracted.

The supplementary material also includes some redundant expansions of certain key expressions that were encountered in our deduction of the algorithm. That section is there to provide clarity, and to explicitly show the size of the matrices involved in particular. Again, those expressions should not be used in a programmatic implementation of the algorithm.

Perhaps the most instructive part of this writing is the worked out example that is included in the supplementary material. Those readers who prefer visual patterns for conveying the matrix-matrix and matrix-vector products will find this very useful. The practice of showing operations using boxes of different sizes is also common in the relevant literature, but it certainly helps to have an example with all indices of the matrix elements in place.

Finally, it is the hope of the author that this material will motivate others to write long form white papers with sufficient technical content. This writing provides an analytical framework for formally expressing the backpropagation algorithm for other (more complex) neural network

architectures (for example the “transformer” that is ubiquitous in modern AI deployments).

Derivatives of feed-forward neural network layers

For a vector-valued function f that is a function of two inputs, a matrix W and a vector x , abstractly expressed as $f = f(W, x)$, two derivatives are realized:

$$\nabla_x f \quad \text{and} \quad \nabla_W f$$

Writing the derivatives in terms of their (Cartesian) components we have:

$$(\nabla_x f(W, x))_{i,j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} f_i \quad \text{and} \quad (\nabla_W f(W, x))_{i,jk} = \frac{\partial}{\partial w_{jk}} f_i$$

Being verbose, the equation for the ∇_x derivatives is obtained from the vector form of the expression for f that uses Einstein summation over the basis vectors:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_x f(W, x) &= \nabla_x (f_i(W, x) \hat{e}_i) \\ &= \hat{e}_j \otimes \hat{e}_i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} f_i(W, x) \quad (\text{the } \hat{e}_i \text{ commutes the derivative}) \end{aligned}$$

which describe the Jacobian matrix, and the Cartesian coordinate system is implied. Formally, the components are extracted by projecting to both sets of basis vectors $\{\hat{e}_j\}, \{\hat{e}_i\}$. It is similar for the gradient with respect to the components of a matrix.

For the specific case where f is a matrix-vector product of the inputs in the order they appear, $f = Wx$, we have:

$$(\nabla_x f(W, x))_{i,j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (W_{im} x_m) = W_{im} \delta_{mj} = W_{ij}$$

and

$$(\nabla_W f(W, x))_{i,jk} = \frac{\partial}{\partial w_{jk}} (W_{im} x_m) = \delta_{ij} \delta_{mk} x_m = \delta_{ij} x_k$$

Here is a concrete example for $f \in \mathbb{R}^2$, $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$ in multi-equation form:

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 &= W_{11}x_1 + W_{12}x_2 + W_{13}x_3 \\ f_2 &= W_{21}x_1 + W_{22}x_2 + W_{23}x_3 \end{aligned}$$

with derivatives:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_1} = W_{11} & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_2} = W_{12} & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_3} = W_{13} \\ \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_1} = W_{21} & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_2} = W_{22} & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_3} = W_{23} \end{array}$$

and:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial W_{11}} = \delta_{11}x_1 = x_1 & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial W_{12}} = \delta_{11}x_2 = x_2 & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial W_{13}} = \delta_{11}x_3 = x_3 \\ \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial W_{21}} = \delta_{12}x_1 = 0 & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial W_{22}} = \delta_{12}x_2 = 0 & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial W_{23}} = \delta_{12}x_3 = 0 \\ \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial W_{11}} = \delta_{21}x_1 = 0 & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial W_{12}} = \delta_{21}x_2 = 0 & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial W_{13}} = \delta_{21}x_3 = 0 \\ \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial W_{21}} = \delta_{22}x_1 = x_1 & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial W_{22}} = \delta_{22}x_2 = x_2 & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial W_{23}} = \delta_{22}x_3 = x_3 \end{array}$$

In the case where we have a layer of a deep neural network, the result is obtained in a similar way. We have a vector-valued function $z = z(W, x)$, which is an affine function that represents

$z = Ax + b$, where A is a non-square matrix and b is a vector. Here, the input matrix W comprises of A and absorbs the bias vector b as its last column (as is customary for feed-forward neural networks). Now our notation needs to be different, as the summation implied by a repeated index will not work directly.

For the derivatives with respect to the input vector, we have the same equation for the components as earlier. Assume that the last column of W that contains the bias vector is indicated by the index J . Then we can write:

$$(\nabla_x z(W, x))_{i,j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (W_{im}x_m + W_{iJ}) = W_{im}\delta_{mj} = W_{ij}$$

and the only difference is that the implied summation is over the number of elements of the x vector instead of the total number of columns, J , of the matrix W ; we are abusing our notation, but $j \neq J$ always.

The derivatives with respect to the components of W are obtained in a similar fashion, with some of the notation slightly abused. Again, with J indicating the last column of W , let me write the generic form like this:

$$(\nabla_W z(W, x))_{i,jk} = \frac{\partial}{\partial W_{jk}} (W_{im}x_m + W_{iJ}) = \delta_{ij}\delta_{mk}x_m + \delta_{ij}\delta_{Jk}$$

and stop there, with the simplification $\delta_{mk}x_m = x_k$ not exercised on purpose. Again, the summation implied by the repeated index m runs up to the number of elements of the vector x . This notation now works for the first term; when $k = J$, to extract the derivatives with respect to the last column of W , the δ_{mk} term that participates in the sum will never hit $m = J$, and will never contribute to those derivatives. Meanwhile, for the $k = J$ instances, the second term will be 1 for $i = j$, which ends up extracting the J^{th} column for each row i .

Here is a specific example that expands on the previous example by adding the biases:

$$\begin{aligned} z_1 &= W_{11}x_1 + W_{12}x_2 + W_{13}x_3 + W_{14} \\ z_2 &= W_{21}x_1 + W_{22}x_2 + W_{23}x_3 + W_{24} \end{aligned}$$

with W derivatives:

$$\begin{array}{cccc} \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial W_{11}} = \delta_{11}x_1 = x_1 & \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial W_{12}} = \delta_{11}x_2 = x_2 & \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial W_{13}} = \delta_{11}x_3 = x_3 & \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial W_{14}} = \delta_{11}\delta_{44} = 1 \\ \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial W_{21}} = \delta_{12}x_1 = 0 & \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial W_{22}} = \delta_{12}x_2 = 0 & \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial W_{23}} = \delta_{12}x_3 = 0 & \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial W_{24}} = \delta_{12}\delta_{44} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial W_{11}} = \delta_{21}x_1 = 0 & \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial W_{12}} = \delta_{21}x_2 = 0 & \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial W_{13}} = \delta_{21}x_3 = 0 & \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial W_{14}} = \delta_{21}\delta_{44} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial W_{21}} = \delta_{22}x_1 = x_1 & \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial W_{22}} = \delta_{22}x_2 = x_2 & \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial W_{23}} = \delta_{22}x_3 = x_3 & \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial W_{24}} = \delta_{22}\delta_{44} = 1 \end{array}$$

(And in this way we have *generating equations* that we can use for guiding the programming of the training part of such a network.)

Expanded forms of select expressions

The M and $\bar{\sigma}$ functions for a single layer

With Eq. (5) we have a form of function composition that represents the neural network function, y . We said that the $M_l(\cdot)$ functions are affine, and the output layer's function, $M_o(\cdot)$, may be “linear” depending on the application, implying that there can be no bias terms. In this section, we give an example of how the M and $\bar{\sigma}$ functions operate.

Here is what the first affine layer operation that produces the vector of preactivations looks like when written explicitly in terms of the vector components

$$z^{(1)} = M_1(x) = \begin{pmatrix} \underbrace{w_{11}^{(1)} x_1 + w_{12}^{(1)} x_2 + \cdots + w_{1N}^{(1)} x_N}_{\text{linear}} + \underbrace{w_{1(N+1)}^{(1)}}_{\text{bias}} \\ w_{21}^{(1)} x_1 + w_{22}^{(1)} x_2 + \cdots + w_{2N}^{(1)} x_N + w_{2(N+1)}^{(1)} \\ \vdots \\ w_{n^{(2)}1}^{(1)} x_1 + w_{n^{(2)}2}^{(1)} x_2 + \cdots + w_{n^{(2)}N}^{(1)} x_N + w_{n^{(2)}(N+1)}^{(1)} \end{pmatrix}$$

Take note of the subscripts that are used for the i, j (row, column) indices of the matrix of weights and biases, $w^{(1)}$. There are numbers such as N and $n^{(2)}$, which are the number of input nodes and the number of nodes of layer 2, respectively, as well as $N + 1$, for the index of the column corresponding to the embedded bias terms.

Here is an even more verbose form for the arbitrary layer l , where the vector of activations that is the input to this layer is endowed with a 1 in order to embed the addition of the bias term in a matrix-vector multiplication:

$$\begin{pmatrix} z_1^{(l)} \\ z_2^{(l)} \\ \vdots \\ z_{n^{(l)}}^{(l)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(l)} & w_{12}^{(l)} & w_{13}^{(l)} & \cdots & w_{1n^{(l-1)}}^{(l)} & w_{1(n^{(l-1)}+1)}^{(l)} \\ w_{21}^{(l)} & w_{22}^{(l)} & w_{23}^{(l)} & \cdots & w_{2n^{(l-1)}}^{(l)} & w_{2(n^{(l-1)}+1)}^{(l)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ w_{n^{(l)}1}^{(l)} & w_{n^{(l)}2}^{(l)} & w_{n^{(l)}3}^{(l)} & \cdots & w_{n^{(l)}n^{(l-1)}}^{(l)} & w_{n^{(l)}(n^{(l-1)}+1)}^{(l)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_1^{(l-1)} \\ a_2^{(l-1)} \\ \vdots \\ a_{n^{(l-1)}}^{(l-1)} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The vector of activations is obtained by componentwise evaluation of the activation function, $\sigma(\cdot)$, that is inside the function $\bar{\sigma}(\cdot)$, as:

$$a^{(l)} = \bar{\sigma}(z^{(l)}) = \begin{pmatrix} a_1^{(l)} \\ a_2^{(l)} \\ \vdots \\ a_{n^{(l)}}^{(l)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma(z_1^{(l)}) \\ \sigma(z_2^{(l)}) \\ \vdots \\ \sigma(z_{n^{(l)}}^{(l)}) \end{pmatrix}$$

I offer a clarification on the notation: the $\bar{\sigma}(\cdot)$ function ingests a preactivation vector, z , and feeds each of its components into the scalar function $\sigma(\cdot)$ to produce the components of the activation vector, a .

The Jacobian of the neural network function

We encountered an over-simplified expression in pp. 5, where the neural network function, $y(\theta, x)$, is differentiated with respect to an arbitrary parameter in the network, λ . That was a consequence of our notation using θ as a vector of all the neural network parameters, and λ is just one of them. The expression shows a column vector of derivatives of the output vector taken with respect to a single neural network parameter:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} y(\theta, x) = \nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} y(\theta^{(0)}, \theta^{(L)}, \theta^{(L-1)}, \dots, \theta^{(l)}, \dots, \theta^{(2)}, \theta^{(1)}, x) \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \theta^{(l)}$$

Here is an example where λ is the q^{th} variable in the $\theta^{(l)}$ vector of parameters, corresponding to the l^{th} layer:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_q^{(l)}} \\ \frac{\partial y_2}{\partial \theta_q^{(l)}} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial y_M}{\partial \theta_q^{(l)}} \end{pmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \\ \frac{\partial y_2}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial y_2}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial y_2}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial y_4}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial y_4}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial y_4}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}}{\partial \theta_q^{(l)}} \\ \frac{\partial \theta_q^{(l)}}{\partial \theta_q^{(l)}} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}}{\partial \theta_q^{(l)}} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \\ \frac{\partial y_2}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial y_2}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial y_2}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial y_4}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial y_4}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial y_4}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \vdots \\ \vdots \\ 1 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix} \quad (q^{\text{th}} \text{ row}) \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_q^{(l)}} \\ \frac{\partial y_2}{\partial \theta_q^{(l)}} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial y_{n^{(l)}}}{\partial \theta_q^{(l)}} \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

This vector is the q^{th} column in the subset of columns of the $\nabla_{\theta} y$ Jacobian matrix that correspond to the parameter set $\theta^{(l)}$. Here, I have used LAST to indicate the last component of the $\theta^{(l)}$ vector, which is the number $n^{(l)} \times (n^{(l-1)} + 1)$, because we have stacked parameters of the l^{th} layer in a long column (vector) of that many components.

Such an equation will never be used in practice, and it is here to aid in understanding the material.

The “forward” chain-rule differentiation cascading used in the text

The very first application of the chain rule (through Jacobian matrix multiplication) for expressing the gradients of the neural network with respect to the parameters of an arbitrary layer, l , is Eq. (9). This equation expresses how upstream gradients with respect to network parameters affect the output through the affine (or “linear”) layer prior to the output:

$$\nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} y(x) = \left(\nabla_{\xi} (M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi)) \right) \nabla_{\theta^{(l)}} a^{(L)}$$

The outer-most function of the network, M_o , is differentiated with respect to its argument, $a^{(L)}$, which is the vector of activations from layer L (the last hidden layer), and is shown here by the generic vector variable ξ . The vector-valued function $M_o(a^{(L)})$ looks like this:

$$M_o[\theta^{(o)}](a^{(L)}) = \begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(o)} a_1^{(L)} + w_{12}^{(o)} a_2^{(L)} + \cdots + w_{1n^{(L)}}^{(o)} a_{n^{(L)}}^{(L)} + w_{1(n^{(L)}+1)}^{(o)} \\ w_{21}^{(o)} a_1^{(L)} + w_{22}^{(o)} a_2^{(L)} + \cdots + w_{2n^{(L)}}^{(o)} a_{n^{(L)}}^{(L)} + w_{2(n^{(L)}+1)}^{(o)} \\ \vdots \\ w_{M1}^{(o)} a_1^{(L)} + w_{M2}^{(o)} a_2^{(L)} + \cdots + w_{Mn^{(L)}}^{(o)} a_{n^{(L)}}^{(L)} + w_{M(n^{(L)}+1)}^{(o)} \end{pmatrix}$$

Here, I have retained the parameterization of the function via the vector $\theta^{(o)} = (w_{11}^{(o)}, w_{12}^{(o)}, \dots, w_{M(n^{(L)}+1)}^{(o)})^T$. Note that this output layer has biases added to the outputs. With the dummy variable it looks like this:

$$M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi) = \begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(o)} \xi_1 + w_{12}^{(o)} \xi_2 + \cdots + w_{1n^{(L)}}^{(o)} \xi_{n^{(L)}} + w_{1(n^{(L)}+1)}^{(o)} \\ w_{21}^{(o)} \xi_1 + w_{22}^{(o)} \xi_2 + \cdots + w_{2n^{(L)}}^{(o)} \xi_{n^{(L)}} + w_{2(n^{(L)}+1)}^{(o)} \\ \vdots \\ w_{M1}^{(o)} \xi_1 + w_{M2}^{(o)} \xi_2 + \cdots + w_{Mn^{(L)}}^{(o)} \xi_{n^{(L)}} + w_{M(n^{(L)}+1)}^{(o)} \end{pmatrix}$$

Its Jacobian matrix with respect to the components of its argument looks like this:

$$\nabla_{\xi} M_o(\xi) = \begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(o)} & w_{12}^{(o)} & \cdots & w_{1n^{(L)}}^{(o)} \\ w_{21}^{(o)} & w_{22}^{(o)} & \cdots & w_{2n^{(L)}}^{(o)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ w_{M1}^{(o)} & w_{M2}^{(o)} & \cdots & w_{Mn^{(L)}}^{(o)} \end{pmatrix}$$

Here is the expanded form of the multiplied Jacobian:

$$\underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial y_1}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \\ \frac{\partial y_2}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial y_2}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial y_2}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial y_M}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial y_M}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial y_M}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \end{pmatrix}}_{M \times \text{LAST}} = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(o)} & w_{12}^{(o)} & \cdots & w_{1n^{(L)}}^{(o)} \\ w_{21}^{(o)} & w_{22}^{(o)} & \cdots & w_{2n^{(L)}}^{(o)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ w_{M1}^{(o)} & w_{M2}^{(o)} & \cdots & w_{Mn^{(L)}}^{(o)} \end{pmatrix}}_{M \times n^{(L)}} \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial a_1^{(L)}}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial a_1^{(L)}}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial a_1^{(L)}}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \\ \frac{\partial a_2^{(L)}}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial a_2^{(L)}}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial a_2^{(L)}}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial a_{n^{(L)}}^{(L)}}{\partial \theta_1^{(l)}} & \frac{\partial a_{n^{(L)}}^{(L)}}{\partial \theta_2^{(l)}} & \cdots & \frac{\partial a_{n^{(L)}}^{(L)}}{\partial \theta_{\text{LAST}}^{(l)}} \end{pmatrix}}_{n^{(L)} \times \text{LAST}}$$

where LAST is the index of the last element of $\theta^{(l)}$, which is $(n^{(l-1)} + 1)n^{(l)}$. This is because there are $n^{(l-1)}$ nodes that are inputs into each of the $n^{(l)}$ nodes of layer l , and the parameters of the layer are stacked by node in the layer (all parameters for node 1 are the first in the stack, etc).

An example of a small deep feed-forward neural network

Consider a feed-forward, deep neural network with 3 input nodes and 2 output nodes. And let the network have 3 fully-connected (affine) hidden layers, and where the 1st and 3rd hidden layers contain 3 nodes, and the 2nd layer 4 nodes. Also let the output nodes be connected to the last hidden layer with a “linear” function, so that there are no bias terms. The activation function at all hidden nodes is $\sigma(\cdot)$. In function composition form, as in Eq. (5), the network looks like this:

$$y = f_o \circ f_3 \circ f_2 \circ f_1(x) = \underbrace{M_o}_{f_o} \circ \underbrace{\bar{\sigma}_3 \circ M_3}_{f_3} \circ \underbrace{\bar{\sigma}_2 \circ M_2}_{f_2} \circ \underbrace{\bar{\sigma}_1 \circ M_1}_{f_1}(x)$$

Let’s express with expanded notation how information flows through this network by constructing all the intermediate preactivations and activations. The preactivations and activations at layer 1 look like this:

$$\begin{pmatrix} z_1^{(1)} \\ z_2^{(1)} \\ z_3^{(1)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(1)} & w_{12}^{(1)} & w_{13}^{(1)} & w_{14}^{(1)} \\ w_{21}^{(1)} & w_{22}^{(1)} & w_{23}^{(1)} & w_{24}^{(1)} \\ w_{31}^{(1)} & w_{32}^{(1)} & w_{33}^{(1)} & w_{34}^{(1)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} a_1^{(1)} \\ a_2^{(1)} \\ a_3^{(1)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma(z_1^{(1)}) \\ \sigma(z_2^{(1)}) \\ \sigma(z_3^{(1)}) \end{pmatrix}$$

The preactivations and activations at layer 2 look like this:

$$\begin{pmatrix} z_1^{(2)} \\ z_2^{(2)} \\ z_3^{(2)} \\ z_4^{(2)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(2)} & w_{12}^{(2)} & w_{13}^{(2)} & w_{14}^{(2)} \\ w_{21}^{(2)} & w_{22}^{(2)} & w_{23}^{(2)} & w_{24}^{(2)} \\ w_{31}^{(2)} & w_{32}^{(2)} & w_{33}^{(2)} & w_{34}^{(2)} \\ w_{41}^{(2)} & w_{42}^{(2)} & w_{43}^{(2)} & w_{44}^{(2)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_1^{(1)} \\ a_2^{(1)} \\ a_3^{(1)} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} a_1^{(2)} \\ a_2^{(2)} \\ a_3^{(2)} \\ a_4^{(2)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma(z_1^{(2)}) \\ \sigma(z_2^{(2)}) \\ \sigma(z_3^{(2)}) \\ \sigma(z_4^{(2)}) \end{pmatrix}$$

The preactivations and activations at layer 3 look like this:

$$\begin{pmatrix} z_1^{(3)} \\ z_2^{(3)} \\ z_3^{(3)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(3)} & w_{12}^{(3)} & w_{13}^{(3)} & w_{14}^{(3)} & w_{15}^{(3)} \\ w_{21}^{(3)} & w_{22}^{(3)} & w_{23}^{(3)} & w_{24}^{(3)} & w_{25}^{(3)} \\ w_{31}^{(3)} & w_{32}^{(3)} & w_{33}^{(3)} & w_{34}^{(3)} & w_{35}^{(3)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_1^{(2)} \\ a_2^{(2)} \\ a_3^{(2)} \\ a_4^{(2)} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} a_1^{(3)} \\ a_2^{(3)} \\ a_3^{(3)} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma(z_1^{(3)}) \\ \sigma(z_2^{(3)}) \\ \sigma(z_3^{(3)}) \end{pmatrix}$$

The linear output layer looks like this:

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(o)} & w_{12}^{(o)} & w_{13}^{(o)} \\ w_{21}^{(o)} & w_{22}^{(o)} & w_{23}^{(o)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_1^{(3)} \\ a_2^{(3)} \\ a_3^{(3)} \end{pmatrix}$$

In order to “train” this network, a cost function, C , is needed also, and we will assume that it has the form given by Eq. (6). Recall that what we are after is expressions for the components of the gradient of the loss function with respect to the network’s parameters such that the update equation can be used. We will make use of Eq. (14), where we construct for each input the error and use “backpropagation” to accumulate the quantities that are the components of the gradient vector of the loss function, $\nabla_{\theta} C$

First let’s express the gradient of the cost function by making use of Eq. (15) and the definitions of the $A^{(m)}$, M' , and $D^{(m)}$ matrices. We will stack the vectors that Eq. (15) produces to get a

global view. We have:

$$\nabla_{\theta} C = 2 \sum_m \begin{pmatrix} A_1^{(m)} D_1^{(m)} M'_2 D_2^{(m)} M'_3 D_3^{(m)} M'_o r^{(m)} \\ A_2^{(m)} D_2^{(m)} M'_3 D_3^{(m)} M'_o r^{(m)} \\ A_3^{(m)} D_3^{(m)} M'_o r^{(m)} \\ A_o^{(m)} r^{(m)} \end{pmatrix} \begin{array}{l} 3 \times 4 \text{ rows} \\ 4 \times 4 \text{ rows} \\ 3 \times 5 \text{ rows} \\ 2 \times 3 \text{ rows} \end{array}$$

and a vector of $12 + 16 + 15 + 6 = 49$ components.

The M' matrices are:

$$M'_2 = \left(\nabla_{\xi} M_2[\theta^{(2)}](\xi) \right)^T = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(2)} & w_{12}^{(2)} & w_{13}^{(2)} \\ w_{21}^{(2)} & w_{22}^{(2)} & w_{23}^{(2)} \\ w_{31}^{(2)} & w_{32}^{(2)} & w_{33}^{(2)} \\ w_{41}^{(2)} & w_{42}^{(2)} & w_{43}^{(2)} \end{pmatrix}^T}_{\text{affine excluding bias}}$$

$$M'_3 = \left(\nabla_{\xi} M_3[\theta^{(3)}](\xi) \right)^T = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(3)} & w_{12}^{(3)} & w_{13}^{(3)} & w_{14}^{(3)} \\ w_{21}^{(3)} & w_{22}^{(3)} & w_{23}^{(3)} & w_{24}^{(3)} \\ w_{31}^{(3)} & w_{32}^{(3)} & w_{33}^{(3)} & w_{34}^{(3)} \end{pmatrix}^T}_{\text{affine excluding bias}}$$

$$M'_o = \left(\nabla_{\xi} M_o[\theta^{(o)}](\xi) \right)^T = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} w_{11}^{(o)} & w_{12}^{(o)} & w_{13}^{(o)} \\ w_{21}^{(o)} & w_{22}^{(o)} & w_{23}^{(o)} \end{pmatrix}^T}_{\text{linear}}$$

which are the transposes of the “linear” part of the matrix of parameters that embeds the weights. (In a more conventional notation where biases are not embedded in the matrix, it would just be the transposes of the weight matrices.)

The D' matrices (ignoring the m data instance notation) are:

$$D_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma'(z_1^{(1)}) & & & \\ & \sigma'(z_2^{(1)}) & & \\ & & \sigma'(z_3^{(1)}) & \\ & & & \sigma'(z_4^{(1)}) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma'(z_1^{(2)}) & & & & \\ & \sigma'(z_2^{(2)}) & & & \\ & & \sigma'(z_3^{(2)}) & & \\ & & & \sigma'(z_4^{(2)}) & \\ & & & & \sigma'(z_5^{(2)}) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$D_3 = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma'(z_1^{(3)}) & & & \\ & \sigma'(z_2^{(3)}) & & \\ & & \sigma'(z_3^{(3)}) & \\ & & & \sigma'(z_4^{(3)}) \end{pmatrix}$$

Here the matrices are diagonal and the primed function, $\sigma'(\cdot)$, indicates a total derivative of the $\sigma(\cdot)$ function with respect to its argument. The different rows show the specific components of the preactivations that are used to evaluate the derivatives of $\sigma(\cdot)$.

